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MICRONEEDLE: AN OVERVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The most frequent modalities for transdermal medication administration include hypodermic needles, topical creams, and transdermal patches. Because the stratum corneum layer of the skin functions as a barrier for molecules, only a few molecules reach the site of action, most therapeutic medications have a limited effect. This page discusses the various varieties of microneedles and how they are made. Thenumerous types of microneedles and how they are created are also discussed on this page.Microneedles are a novel type of delivery method that helps to improve medication distribution through this route while also solving the issues that come with traditional formulations. The fundamental premise entails disrupting the skin layer, resulting in micron-sized channels that lead the drug directly to the epidermis or upper dermis region, where it can bypass the barrier and enter the systemic circulation.This technique is now being used in a variety of fields, including oligonucleotide distribution, vaccine delivery, insulin delivery, and even cosmetics delivery. Many microneedle products have entered the market in recent years. Although, before the microneedles can be successfully launched into the market, much study must be done to solve the many problems. The third piece of this examination looks at the issues and obstacles that come with using microneedles. The traditional way of delivering a drug to patient was painful but by using the microneedle it was quite painless which improves the patient compliance and the delivery of potent medication easier which avoids dose dumping and help in therapeutic effectiveness.

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INTRODUCTION

MN was firstly conceptualized in 1970s by Martin S. Gerstel and Virgil A. Place [1,2] the report was published in the late 90s.[1,3]It was employed as a drug delivery device to transport a drug directly to the dermis layer via percutaneous injection, resulting in a local and systemic pharmacological impact. It has been utilised to increase the bioavailability of proteinaceous medicines, in addition to its painless behaviour, it has been used to increase the bioavailability of proteinaceous drugs, [1,4] and it has been shown to be effective. MNs have enabled the transdermal delivery of even the most complicated compounds, such as proteins, vaccines, and peptides. Microneedles come in a variety of shapes and sizes, including solid, hollow, coated, and dissolving, but they are all employed to deliver drugs quickly and efficiently. [1,5]The device is known as a microneedle patch when microneedles are produced in arrays on a backing that can be applied to the skin like a bandage. (Hentry and colleagues, 1998). Microneedles are classified as hollow, solid, coated, or polymer. [11]

The purpose of microneedle to administer a wide range of low molecular weight drugs, biotherapeutics, and vaccines, including a number of small molecule and protein drugs and vaccines that have been studied in humans.

The main Objectives of these paper is to review the published scientific literatures relating to microneedle benefits,types,measurements,fabrication properties,evaluation,future prospectives and applications.

DEFINITION

The microneedle-mediated delivery system, which is defined as the non-invasive delivery of medications through the skin surface, [6,7] which consists of an array of submillimetre-sized needles (up to 1500 m in length) attached to a base support, has been shown to penetrate into the viable epidermis of the skin, bypassing the stratum corneum (SC), the skin's outermost layer, has been shown to be able to penetrate into the viable epidermis of [6,8]

BENEFITS OF MICRONEEDLES

- The action takes place quickly.
- the active pharmaceutical substance is administered without pain.
- Large molecules can be given out.
- There is no first-pass metabolism.
- quicker healing at the injection site compared with a hypodermic needle
- Due to the convenience of administration, patients comply.
- Significantly reduced microbial penetration when compared to a hypodermic needle since the microneedle avoids puncturing the stratum corneum and only punctures the epidermis.
- Drug distribution can be localised to a specific location of the skin.
- Good repeatability, stability, and increased medication efficacy may lead to dose reduction.
- excellent tolerability with no long-term oedema or erythema. [9]

DRAWBACKS of microneedle

- Skin irritation can occur due to allergies or sensitive skin, and local inflammation can occur if the drug concentration is high beneath the skin.
- If the device is not held vertically, the dose may escape or penetrate the skin to varying degrees. Because the thickness of the stratum corneum and other layers of the skin differs between people, particle penetration depth may also differ.
- The outside environment, such as skin moisture, may have an impact on delivery.
- When the patch is removed, the tip of the microneedle may break off and remain inside the skin.
- Hollow microneedles can be obstructed by compressed cutaneous tissue. [9]

MICRONEEDLE MEASUREMENTS

Since the epidermis is up to 1500 micron thick and a needle length of up to 1500 micron is sufficient to release medication into the epidermis, microneedles can be made in a variety of sizes depending on the type of microneedle and the material utilised. Needles that are longer and thicker in diameter can penetrate deep into the dermis, causing nerve injury and pain. They are typically 150-1500 microns long, 50-250 microns wide, and 1-25 microns thick at the tip. As previously stated, a microneedle device is required. The needle diameter is kept between a few microns to create a micron-sized transport route. Microneedle tips come in a variety of shapes, including cylindrical, triangular, pentagonal, and octagonal. [10]

MICRONEEDLE PATCH IDEAL CHARACTERISTICS

The produced microneedles must be capable of deep insertion into the skin without breaking, with a length or height range of 50 to 900 μ m and a diameter of 1 μ m. MNs should be the right size. These must be able to sustain a force of roughly 10N and have enough mechanical stability. These are likewise designed to dispense medications at a predetermined rate in a controlled manner. Similar to a hypodermic needle, these should have a quick beginning of action and efficient drug administration. These were created to help with self-medication and tailored medication at various dose levels. These items need to be more durable, and they should be leak-proof when administering liquid medications. These patches must adhere to the skin as well as normal transdermal patches. [1] In the case of optimal microneedles, effective attributes include microneedle design that minimises pain. [11] The majority of microneedles are made of glass, silicone (which is brittle), stainless steel, solid or coated gold over nickel, palladium, cobalt, and platinum, and biodegradable polymers. [11]

MICRONEEDLE FABRICATION MATERIAL AND ITS PROPERTIES

Table No.1 Microneedle fabrication material and its properties.

Type	Material used	Properties
Silicon	Silicon	Crystalline, brittle Elastic and flexible
Metal	Stainless steel and titanium, palladium, nickel, palladium cobalt alloys	Good biocompatibility, Strong Metal, non-biodegradable, expensive
Ceramic(ormocer-modified)	Alumina, calcium sulphate dehydrate(gypsum)and calcium phosphate dehydrate(brushite)	Three dimensional Cross linked polymer
Silica glass	Silica, Borosilicate glass, boron trioxide	Inert and brittle in nature
Carbohydrates	Maltose, others sugars- mannitol,trehalose,sucrose,xylitol and galactose	Cheap and safe Degraded (at high temp.)
Biodegradable Polymer	polylactic acid, polylactic co- glycolic acid,polyglycolic acid, polyvinylpyrrolidone, poly carbonate, polyvinyl maleic anhydride, SU-8 photoresist,Polymethyl methacrylate,	Biodegradable Tougher than glass and ceramic Good resistance biocompatible
Non-Biodegradable polymer	Polyvinyl acetate, alginic acid, gantrez AN-139, copolymer of methyvinylether and Maleic auhydride,carbipol 971 P-NF,Polyetherimide, cyclic – olefin copolymer	Non-biodegradable Good resistance
Polysaccharides	Carboxymethylcellulose, amylopectin, maltose, dextran, Thermoplastic starch, chondroitin sulfate	Biodegradable,rapid drug delivery

MECHANISM of action

MNs have been designed in such a way that they can combine the benefits of both hypodermic needles and transdermal patches in order to deliver drugs through the skin in therapeutically desirable quantities. Because of their length and pore size, MNs differ significantly from hypodermic needles (ranging from sub-microns to millimetres). [13] The mechanism of action is determined by the design of the microneedle. The general mechanism of delivery via [9] microneedle array composed of hundreds of microneedles with lengths less than 1 mm long [12] is based on mechanical disruption of the skin and application of the drug or vaccine within the epidermis, from which it can more easily reach its targeted site of action. [9] Furthermore, microneedles create micro-scale drug delivery channels without interfering with the blood vessels and nerve endings found in viable epidermis and dermis. After being inserted into the skin, these microneedles immediately release the drug into the dermis. [12] Gill et al. investigated the effect of MN geometry (using MNs with varying lengths, thicknesses, widths, tip angles, and the number of MNs on a patch) on pain when compared to a 26-gage hypodermal needle. All of the MNs tested were 5% to 40% less painful than the chosen hypodermic needle. The thickness, width, and tip angle had no effect on pain. However, reducing the number and length of MNs significantly reduced pain. Furthermore, increasing the number of MNs by tenfold resulted in a twofold increase in pain (by score). They also discovered that a threefold increase in MN length caused a sevenfold increase in pain. [13]

TYPES OF MICRONEEDLES

Silicon, stainless steel, sugar, and polymers have all been used to create solid, coated, hollow, or dissolvable microneedles (Figure 1). Each type of microneedle has its own set of characteristics, benefits, drawbacks, applications, and material type. [14]

Figure 1: depicts various types of microneedles: (a) for pre-treatment of the skin, solid microneedles with a poke with patch approach are used. (b) coated microneedles employ the coat and poke method, in which a drug solution coating is applied to the needle surface. (c) biodegradable polymers are used to make dissolving microneedles. (d) the drug is deposited in the dermis via hollow microneedles filled with the drug solution.

Solid Microneedle

This type of microneedle structure is intended to penetrate the stratum carenum in order to improve drug delivery to the dermis and kinetic transport across the skin. Microneedle vaccine delivery is preferable because it lasts longer and produces a more robust antibody response [14,16]. When compared to hollow microneedles, solid microneedles are easier to manufacture, have superior mechanical properties, and sharper tips. Furthermore, the solid microneedle can be made of a variety of materials, including silicon, metals, and polymers. (See Figure 2) [14]

Figure 2: Solid Microneedles Made of Silicon

(A–D), Metals (E–H), And Polymer (I–L)

Figure 3: Hollow Microneedles.

Hollow Microneedle

The hollow microneedle has a hollow/empty core/chamber where drug fluid is injected/stored (Figure 3) [14,10]. The hollow microneedle, as opposed to the solid microneedle, can handle a larger dose/amount of drug solution. A hollow microneedle can also deliver drugs into the viable epidermis or dermis, which is ideal for high molecular weight compounds [14,7]. Furthermore, it regulates drug release over time, making it suitable for use with liquid vaccine formulations [14,17]. Hollow microneedles, unlike solid microneedles, are an active drug delivery method that establish a conduit for drug diffusion into the dermis based on a non-pressurized drug reservoir. Hollow microneedle material formulation and production factors can be used to enable customizable release kinetics. Pharmaceuticals with higher concentrations can have burst release characteristics, whereas matrix-loaded drugs can have a steady-state drug release that lasts days to weeks, depending on the application. Hollow microneedles, like hypodermic needles, can be constructed to allow for flow rate and pressure control. Microneedle aspect ratio (height to base diameter ratio) and other process parameters can be adjusted for quick release, delayed infusion, or a time-varying delivery rate.

The hollow microneedle has been effectively used in a number of vaccinations and inoculations over the years. [14,18] However, in comparison to the solid microneedle, the hollow microneedle has received less attention because it is weaker and requires more care in terms of needle design and insertion procedure. Furthermore, during the injection procedure, the hollow microneedle has technical issues such as leakage and blockage. [14,18]

Figure 3: Knife hollow microneedles 29: (a) an array of tapered metal microneedles next to the tip of a 26-gauge hypodermic needle, and (b) a single tapered metal microneedle created by electro-deposition onto a polymeric mould. [15] Optical and scanning electron microscopy images of hollow microneedles made of silicon, metal, and glass. [14] (A) A 100-needle array manufactured by electrodeposition onto a polymer mould (200 m tall) yields a straight-walled metal microneedle. (B) A tapered, bevelled glass microneedle created with a typical micropipette puller (shown in 900 m length). Fabrication methodologies and transport investigations for microfabricated needles for transdermal administration of macromolecules and nanoparticles. [14]

Coated Microneedle

This is a solid-type MN that has been coated with a drug solution. Depending on the thickness of the coating layer, it normally carries a smaller amount of the medicine. The capacity to properly coat a regulated drug layer onto mns is critical to the effectiveness of medication delivery employing coated MNs. A MN that has been coated has the ability to transport proteins and DNA with minimum invasiveness. A coated MN has the benefit of delivering the medicine to the skin quickly; but, the leftover drug at the needle's tip may infect other patients. Finally, the results of vaccine delivery utilising coated MN were comparable to vaccinations delivered by intradermal and intramuscular methods. [14,18]

Dissolving microneedle

The dissolvable MN was initially described in 2005 [14,18], and its properties make it a viable method. These properties include allowing quick macromolecule release and a one-step medication application that promotes drug administration simplicity. This strategy is considered better than other approaches due to improvements noticed in applying dissolvable mns following "poke-and-release." A two-step casting procedure allows the dissolvable MN tip to be loaded quickly. The drug-load releases and diffuses quickly by dissolving the needle tip after insertion of the dissolvable MN into the skin [14,18]. The manufacturing of the dissolvable MN is best done with water-soluble components. Similarly, the dissolvable MN is best produced using the micro-mold method of fabrication [14,7]. A dissolvable MN array demands technical expertise to design and manufacture [14,18]. This type of MN, on the other hand, necessitates full insertion, which is typically difficult to achieve, as well as a delay in dissolution [14,10].

Hydrogel-forming microneedles

This is a very new type of microneedle. Microneedles are made from super-swelling polymers. The hydrophilic structure of the polymers allows them to absorb a huge amount of water into their three-dimensional polymeric network. Due to the presence of interstitial fluid, these polymers expand when introduced into the skin. As a result, channels emerge between the capillary circulation and the medication patch. These microneedles are only used to disturb the epidermal barrier prior to needling. They act as a rate-controlling membrane as they swell. They are adaptable in terms of size and shape. The distinctive qualities of such microneedles are their ease of sterilising and safe removal from the skin [10,19]. Migdadi et al investigated the use of hydrogel-forming microneedles to deliver metformin transdermally, reducing the gastrointestinal side effects associated with oral administration. The use of specially engineered microneedles increased medication penetration and bioavailability [10,4]. Swellable microneedles for drug delivery are also made out of cross-linked polymers.

Figure 4: Diagrammatic example of hydrogel creation by hydrogel producing microneedles during skin needling for intradermal medication administration in blood vessels.

DRUG DELIVERY METHODOLOGY

Figure 5: Methodology of Drug Delivery.

FABRICATION OF SOLID MICroneedle

Table 2: Method of fabricating solid microneedle.

Method	Material	Dimensions	Advantages	Disadvantages
Separable dissolving arrow heads	Polydimethylsiloxane (pdms) sylgard 184,) metal shaft ,water-soluble excipients – pvp, sucrose ,PLGA	600 mm-long PVP/PVAarrowhead capped onto a metal shaft with an exposed length of 600 mm and a 100 mm overlap.	Rapid (1–5s)/painless drug/vaccines delivery, rapid (1–5 s)/painless drug/vaccines delivery, convenient/safe/ potential self-administration, can allow controlled release of active does not require extended patch wearing even for long duration of drug releases, PDMS:inert,non-toxic,non flammable.	Difficult insertion into skin as requires wider needle geometry (non-blunt shaft). Non reusable. Fibrotic reaction.
Dissolving	Mixture insulin, water, dextrin	Basal diameter: 3.24 ± 0.16 and 0.55 ± 0.03 mm	Bio-compatible	Produce bio hazardous, sharp waste, Large tipped.
Pyramidal dissolving polymer	Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), polyvinylpyrrolidone (pvp) A:pyramidal mn B:extended pyramidal mns C:pedestal mns	Base width base depth needle height: a: 300 mm 300 mm 600 mm. B: 300 mm 300 mm 900 mm. c: 340 mm 340 mm 900 mm) 10 10 array468	Ability to increase drug capacity and localize to the mn tip. Allowed a deeper insertion. Higher increase of drug to be dissolved.	Produce bio hazardous, Sharp waste.
	Chromium, Silicon wafers	120 mm length, 51 mm tip diameter	Mechanically strong	Reusability questionably, Top 5–10 mm of mn damaged for a few samples.
Dissolving. Fabricated by a drawing technique to create a sharp tip	Maltose	200 mm length 60 mm tip diameter	Requires no moulds, therefore no sharp waste	Complicated process.
Cutting metal using infrared laser, manually bending the mn structure, electropolished	Metal	1000 mm length, 50 mm 200 mm cross section at base, tapered to a sharp tip (angle 20), 106 array468	A short mn insertion time was better than a longer insertion time to facilitate drug permeation	Insertion of large array was difficult by hand, without external device Strong acids used
Silicon master mould to make pdms inverse mould	Sugar glass MN:trehalose/mannitol (50:50 w/w) ,trehalose dehydrate/sucrose (75:25w/w) , trehalose/sucrose (75:25 w/w) ,trehalose/sucrose (50:50 w/w), 2%(w.w) methylene blue	200 mm base 20 mm tip 300 mm height	Fast dissolution of drug into skin, use of simplesugars to create biodegradable mns.	Mn patch needles to be left on the skin for potentially over 20 min
Stainless steel mn produced by chemical etching	Stainless steel	750 mm height , 200 mm 50 mm at the base. Single row of five mns.	Dose of measles vaccine is small, therefore the dimensions of the mn are sufficient to allow coating and delivery of the vaccine, needles long enough for rat	Produce bio hazardous, sharp waste.

				dorsal thickness (700 mm–1000 mm) penetration.
Dissolving MN	Starch/gelatin (1:1 ratio) ,pdms mould	600 mm height 300 mm base 5 mm tip	Cost manufacturing dissolution of five was ,pharmacological retains in starch/gelatine.	effective , rapid minutes achieved activity the injection of insulin.
				Time to reach minimum plasma glucose level ,slightly longer for Mn than for subcutaneous injection

EVALUATION OF MICRONEEDLE

Characterization methods

The drug can be placed onto or into the microneedles in two forms: suspension/dispersion or encapsulated (liposomes, nanoparticles, nanoliposomes) [10,23]. The medicine can be coated or applied as a patch with the polymer solution. Depending on the type of formulation utilised in the microneedles, several physicochemical characterizations such as particle size, polydispersity index, viscosity, and zeta potential can be examined for loaded medication [10,24]. For a patch that is applied following pre-treatment, drug release, adhesion, and penetration tests are done. Dynamic light scattering, X-ray scattering, and transmission electron microscopy can be used to determine the size, internal structure, and crystallinity of liposomes or nanocarriers. Drug dispersion and microneedle stability can be investigated at various temperatures, pH levels, and simulated in-vivo physiological settings (cell line or tissues). Other experiments on developed microneedles include solubility studies, drug content, in-vitro release tests, and biocompatibility studies [10].

Dimensional evaluation

To evaluate the needle geometry and measure the tip radius, length, and height of the microneedle, many approaches are used. Optical or electrical microscopy are the most frequent methods. A 3D image analysis provides a clearer understanding of needle shape and aids in quality control. This was accomplished using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) and a confocal laser microscope. SEM uses a concentrated beam of electrons to create an image of a sample by interacting with the atoms in the sample while scanning and producing various signals that provide information about the sample surface topography and composition. High-resolution images are produced using confocal laser microscopes [10,27,28].

mechanical qualities for incertion forces

A microneedle must be sharp and narrow enough to pierce the skin easily, as well as robust enough not to shatter once inside.

The force at which the microneedle loses its structural integrity and the insertion force are two critical factors for a safe and efficient design of microneedles. The 'safety factor' is the relationship between these two pressures. The higher the ratio, the better [10,26].

in-vitroskin permeation study:

The drug's penetration into the skin is measured using a diffusion cell equipment. The experiment generally uses pig ear skin, which is positioned between the receptor and donor compartments. [10,25] compares the cumulative permeation characteristics of microneedle-treated and untreated skin.

in-vivoAnimal model study:

The investigation can be done with hairless rats. To anaesthetize the animal, a proper procedure must be applied. Trans-epidermal water loss (TEWL), which is assessed before and after micro needling, is one of the characteristics examined. This parameter is measured with a DelfinVapometer [10,25].

CLINICAL TRIALS AND SAFETY ASPECTS

Various pre-clinical studies on microneedles have been conducted and proved to be successful in many areas, but only a few have had success in human subjects. In the year 2001, Kaushik et al conducted the first human investigation on micro-needles. When compared to a 26-gauge hypodermic needle, the goal was to see if the silicon microneedles were small enough to prevent pain. The microneedles were inserted into the forearms of the 12 healthy men and women who agreed to participate in the study. The discomfort induced by microneedles was less than that caused by hypodermic needles, according to the study. Arya and her colleagues conducted tests to see if micro-needles induce local skin reactions and are acceptable to patients. The study involved 15 human participants. The microneedles did not induce any swelling, discomfort, or erythema at the patch application site, according to the study.

The patches were self-administered by the patients without the use of an applicator. These were chosen by the human subjects over traditional needles. The randomised clinical experiment was conducted on 21 males to see if pre-treatment with microneedles improved lidocaine administration. After 60 minutes, a topical lidocaine cream containing 4% lidocaine produced anaesthesia. Within 30 minutes of using the microneedles, anaesthesia was achieved. The therapeutic effects of a hyaluronic acid-based microneedle patch were investigated in a ten-patient open trial to treat psoriasis.

On the skin, calcitriol-beta-methasone ointment was administered. Over this, a microneedle patch was put once a day for a week. When compared to normal cream treatment, the one-week administration considerably reduced psoriatic plaques and was thus found to be effective [10]. Microorganisms (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, and *Candida albicans*) can transfer through microneedle-induced holes in the SC, according to current research (Donnelly, 2010). The manufacturing of sterile microneedle items could be one approach for ensuring patient safety.

The use of sterilising, another important safety feature of microneedles is their insertion force and skin mechanical properties. These microneedles should be able to build up enough strength before or during insertion to pierce the skin or other biological tissues without breaking or bending (Aggarwal, 2004). The overall insertion and fracture force of microneedles is determined by factors such as needle height, tip radius, type of material, base diameter, needle thickness, needle density, and so on. Apart from the aforementioned, microneedles may cause other health problems, such as: (i) local inflammation if the amount of drug is high under the skin, (Escobar, 201); (ii) proper clinician knowledge is required for successful application of microneedle technique; (iii) repetitive injections may collapse veins; and (iv) compressed dermal tissue can block hollow microneedles. and (v) when the patch is removed, the tip of the microneedle may break off and remain within the skin. [12]

APPLICATIONS

Hair regrowth

Figure 6 : Hair regrowth was noticed earlier and faster in the Microneedling treated group at 1 week

Delivery of DNA vaccines

Mikszta et al [16] described the use of microneedle technology to deliver a DNA vaccine using the dip and scrape method. The arrays were dipped in a DNA solution and scraped across the skin of mice *in vivo* several times. Microenhancer arrays boosted the expression of the luciferase reporter gene by 2800 times. Furthermore, immunological responses elicited by microneedle delivery were stronger and less varied than those induced by hypodermic injections. Researchers at Beckett-DickinsonTM found similar results in an animal trial of antibody response to HepB naked plasmid DNA vaccination. This method has the potential to reduce the number of doses and boosters required for immunisation. [3] Human IgG, tetanus toxoid, DNA vaccine, influenza vaccine, hepatitis B vaccine, human papilloma virus vaccine, west Nile virus vaccine, chikungunya virus vaccine, Bacillus Calmette Guerin vaccine, ovalbumin vaccine, live attenuated chimeric JE vaccine (Chimer Ivax)-JE/Flavin virus vaccine, diphtheria, malaria, and coxsacki [9]

Desmopressin delivery:

M. Cormier et al [11] (Alza Corporation, USA) investigated the use of microneedles to deliver desmopressin, a powerful peptide hormone used to treat nocturnal enuresis in infants, as well as diabetes insipidus and haemophilia A. On titanium microneedles with a length of 200 μ m, a maximum width of 170 μ m, and a thickness of 35 μ m, an aqueous film coating of desmopressin acetate was applied. With the use of an impact applicator, a microneedle patch was placed into the skin. Within 15 minutes, a target dose of 20 μ g desmopressin was administered to hairless guinea pigs via a 2 cm² microneedle array. This study showed that transdermal desmopressin delivery is a safe and effective alternative to the currently existing administration routes. [3]

Oligonucleotide delivery:

Lin and colleagues [12] applied the findings of microarray drug delivery *in vitro* to the *in vivo* setting. Iontophoresis and an oligonucleotide, 20-merphosphorothioated oligodeoxynucleotide, were used to transport an oligonucleotide across the skin of hairless guinea pigs. Lin and his colleagues employed solid microneedles etched from stainless steel or titanium sheet that had been manufactured using the poke with patch method. In comparison to intact skin, this delivery technique improved molecule absorption. When iontophoresis was paired with microneedles, the transdermal flux was 100 times higher than when iontophoresis was used alone. [3]

Insulin delivery:

Insulin is one of the most difficult drugs for drug delivery technologists to work with. Microarrays were employed by Martano et al [10] to give insulin to diabetic hairless rats. Solid stainless-steel microneedles with a length of 1mm and a tip width of 75 μ m were implanted into the rat skin and supplied insulin using the poke with patch method. Blood glucose levels continuously declined by up to 80% over a 4-hour period, with the decrease in glucose level being dependent on insulin concentration. [3]

Macromolecules with bioactivity (Biopharmaceuticals)

Microneedle arrays were found to improve the transport of both low and high molecular weight drugs across dermatomed human skin. However, the depth to which the microneedles penetrated the skin had no influence on the transport of either low or high molecular weight compounds. An strategy of preparing dissolving microneedles constituting water-soluble polysaccharides has been done for quick and regulated release of molecules. Low molecular weight heparin, insulin, L-Carnitine, calcein, and bovine serum albumin, desmopressin, recombinant human growth hormone, desmopressin, albumin, calcein, erythropoietin, oligonucleotides, porphyrin precursor 5-aminolevulinic acid (ALA), salmon calcitonin, daniplestim, leuprolide [9]

Medication

Microneedles can help overcome the problems of transdermal drug delivery. Microneedles improve drug absorption and eliminate the need for penetration enhancers, which can cause irritation. Microneedles may potentially help to lessen the risks and consequences of systemic administration. L-ascorbic acid, riboflavin, galanthamine, aspirin docetaxel pilocarpine methotrexate prochlorperazine disylate, lidocaine hydrochloride, ropinirole hydrochloride, phenylephrine, naltrexone, mannitol, glycerol, and others are among the drugs delivered using microneedles. [9]

Phlebotomy

Phlebotomy is the process of drawing blood samples in order to analyse specific blood contents for disease diagnosis. Depending on the method, blood is drawn from capillaries by pricking the skin or from veins by using an evacuated collection tube. Both methods have drawbacks, including heavy bleeding, infection, scarring, fainting, or light-headedness. Fear of needles and the moderate pain connected with the operation may make people reluctant to donate blood. In this instance, painless blood sampling with microneedles can be a good substitute for hypodermic needles. Microneedles in the dermis layer beneath the skin, spaced 500–2000 μ m apart, can be used to extract exact bodily fluids and blood samples from capillaries. Microneedles not only make the procedure pleasant, but they also reduce the number of blood samples required (up to 200 nanolitres). Blood volume necessary for analysis The most important need is that the microneedle penetrate to a suitable depth; thus, care should be made in the microneedle's design, material selection, and size to ensure penetration at low pressure without breakage. In the event of diabetes, which necessitates frequent blood monitoring for assessment of glucose concentration or disease severity, painless hollow microneedle-based micro sampling can be utilised instead of traditional methods for glucose estimation. A level microneedle that looks like a mosquito's proboscis has been produced to collect blood for testing. *In-situ* analysis of biological fluid extraction through capillary action was performed using arrays of 350 μ m long hollow out-of-plane microneedles [9].

Cosmeceuticals

Microneedle technology has piqued the interest of the cosmetics industry, and the majority of cosmetic products lend themselves to it for non-surgical and non-ablative treatment of skin conditions such as ageing (wrinkles, lax skin), scarring (acne, surgical), photo damage, hyperpigmentation (age/brown spots), and hair loss. Microneedles, such as Derma rollers® and stamps, are offered for treating skin issues and improving appearance. Clinical Resolution Laboratory's MTS Dermaroller is a cosmetic device with needles that penetrate the skin to a depth of 0.2–0.3 mm. It has 200 extremely fine stainless-steel needles that puncture the skin and create a micro-channel effect.

CURRENT AND FUTURE PROSPECTIVE

Silicon was used to create the first microneedle. A study was conducted to see if microneedles might be used to more effectively administer medications through the skin. Permeation tests were first performed on cadaver skin to investigate if big molecules such as albumin and insulin could flow through the skin using microneedles. Microneedles delivered big molecules better, according to further research. Many new exciting microneedle concepts are currently being developed that will be of great assistance in the future [10,3]. The microneedle technique is being used to treat a variety of medications, but it must overcome a number of obstacles before reaching the market. It will take a lot more research to get it clinically approved. Skin allergies, redness, and irritation are the most common side effects of microneedles technology.

The microneedle can only hold a certain amount of medication. It's difficult to get hydrophilic and big chemicals through the skin. In the production of these needles, the right material must be chosen, one with sufficient mechanical strength and insertion force. The basic goal is to increase permeability without creating discomfort. A patient may find it difficult to poke with a needle and then apply the patch. If the skin pores do not shut after application, there is a risk of infection [10,7]. To deliver the medicine through the skin, a number of technologies are being developed. In traditional microneedles, various changes have been examined.

One of them is 3M's hollow microneedle. This new method is versatile enough to deliver hundreds of milligrams of proteins straight into the systemic circulation. A combination of ultrasonic and transdermal drug administration is also being investigated to boost drug permeability even more. Thus, microneedles can be created with a number of alterations in order to cleverly transfer the drug through the skin creating a new direction and revolution in the field of trans-dermal drug delivery systems.

CONCLUSION

Microneedles, in the form of a patch or an array, have been identified as a possible carrier for successful transdermal administration of a variety of macromolecular medicines. Several studies have concluded that microneedles should be the primary carriers for improving drug absorption deep into the systemic circulation and offering a painless, effective, and safe method for drug delivery. Microneedles will play an essential part in the development and design of controlled medication delivery systems for a variety of pharmaceuticals in the future. These painless technologies are gradually gaining traction and could become one of the most essential devices for regulated drug delivery in the future. Many new exciting microneedle concepts are currently being developed that will be of great assistance in the future. The microneedle technique is being used to treat a variety of medications.

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ABBREVIATIONS:

Mn-microneedle,
SC-subcutaneous

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors state that the publishing of this paper does not include any conflicts of interest.

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